

summarized in Table 1. SB populations increased with level and duration of water in all environments (Table 2). Populations also

increased from pre-flood to maturity crop stages, irrespective of environment. □

Table 1. Incidence of SB in relation to different rice environments and different growth stages at Ghagharaghat, India, 1987-88.

Rainfed rice environment	Variety	Year	SB incidence (%) at different growth stages				<i>r</i> for different growth stages ^a
			Preflood	Early elongation	Late elongation	Maturity	
Shallow water (to 50 cm water)	Mahsuri	1987	1.5	4.5	4.5	6.5	+0.939
		1988	1.5	3.5	5.5	11.5	+0.956*
Deepwater (50-100 cm)	Chakia 59	1987	2.0	5.0	8.0	5.5	+0.708
		1988	2.5	5.5	9.5	25.5	+0.911
Very deepwater (above 1 m)	Jalmagna	1987	3.0	14.0	15.0	31.5	+0.950*
		1988	4.0	8.0	15.5	44.5	+0.981*
Flood (intermittent) (3 times up to 50 cm during 1987, 4 times up to 100 cm during 1988)	Madhukar	1987	9.5	14.5	16.5	25.0	+0.969*
		1988	-	-	-	-	-
<i>r</i> for different rice environments		1987	+0.937	+0.917	+0.848	+0.802	
		1988	+0.993	+0.862	+0.802	+0.772	

= significant at the 5% level.

Table 2. Stem damage due to SB at different rainfed rice environments and growth stages at Ghagharaghat, India, 1987-88.^a

Rainfed rice Environment	Variety	Year	Damaged stems (no.)			
			Preflood	Early elongation	Late elongation	Maturity
Shallow water (to 50 cm water)	Mahsuri	1987	3	9	9	13
		1988	3	7	11	23
Deepwater (50-100 cm)	Chakia 59	1987	4	10	16	11
		1988	5	11	19	51
Very deepwater (>1 m)	Jalmagna	1987	6	28	30	63
		1988	8	16	31	89
Flooded 2-3 times (to 50 cm) ^b	Madhukar	1987	19	29	33	50

^a200 stems selected diagonally in the field from each environment and at each growth stage. ^bThe 1988 crop failed because of flash flooding for more than 1 mo at crop initiation.

***Beauveria bassiana* (Bals.) Vuill. for biological control of rice hispa (RH) in Assam, India**

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During a routine search for an alternative to insecticides for control of RH *Dicladispa armigera* Olivier (Coleop-

tera, Chrysomelidae), we observed the majority of the test beetles reared in cages were dying of a fungal disease. In most cases, the beetles were found stuck to rice leaves and stems.

We cultured the fungus on potato dextrose agar medium incubated at ±24 °C. Fluffy growth of the fungus was noticed 3 d after inoculation on medium; it sporulated at 7 d. The spores were single-celled, hyaline, globose (0.8-), 1-3.5 µm in diameter, with clustering of conidiogenous rachis.

A hispa adult showing infestation with *Beauveria bassiana*. Magnification 11x.

The fungus was identified as *Beauveria bassiana* (Bals.) Vuillemin; its pathogenicity was confirmed through Koch's postulates.

On RH adults, white frosty fungus growth emerged first through intersegmental membranes of the thorax and abdomen (see figure). Ultimately it covered the whole body and appendages. About 90% of the beetle population tested were killed. □

Arthropod diversity in tropical rice ecosystems

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Most organisms that live in ricefields are exogenous species that colonize the rice crop when cultivation begins. The recruitment phase is followed by an interaction phase, and the species present settle into a community.

A large proportion of the individual organisms are more or less trophically interlinked and unified in their dependence on rice.

Pest management actions are often directed at the community of rice arthropods rather than at individual

species. That makes understanding how the community behaves important. When a particular pest species is affected by specific interventions, such as planting a resistant variety or applying selective insecticides, the community structure may also be affected. When one component is reduced, other species living in the same niche may become more dominant with the removal of competition. The predator guild may be reduced, causing abnormal increases in other pest species.

We studied the dynamic developments in an irrigated rice arthropod community during the dry and wet seasons. In both trials, 20 samples from an insecticide-free, 25- × 100-m² plot at the IRRI farm were collected at 3-d intervals using the CO₂NE sampler in the dry season and using a D-Vac sampling machine in the wet season.

Because populations are indefinitely large, and it is not possible to collect, count, and identify all individuals in a community, the sample was taken to represent members of the community.

Arthropods were sorted into species and counted. Hemipterans predominated in all samples. Species from two guilds—phytophages and predators—were found. The phytophages were composed primarily of pest species, such as leafhoppers and planthoppers. The predators consisted of *Cyrtorhinus lividipennis* and *Microvelia atrolineata* (Fig. 1). Other groups of arthropods, in relatively low numbers, were spiders, coleopterans, hymenopterans, and dipterans.

The Shannon Wiener Index was used to describe species diversity:

$$H(s) = -\sum_{i=1}^s p_i \log p_i$$

where s is the number of species and p_i is the proportional abundance of the i^{th} species.

We calculated $H(s)$ and its standard error for each sampling date. Species diversity increased with crop age to about 3 wk after transplanting, then remained relatively unchanged until harvest (Fig. 2).

The plateau value of $H(s)$ varied

Fig. 1. Arthropods in 2 crops of IR66 grown under submerged conditions. IRRI farm, 1988.

Fig. 2. Shannon-Wiener diversity index in 2 crops of IR66 grown under submerged conditions. IRRI farm, 1988.

between 1.75 and 2.25, implying that arthropod diversity was determined by 6 to 9 species. Those species are ranked by abundance:

Feb-May 1988 (dry season)

Micronecta sp. 1
Microvelia atrolineata
Nephotettix virescens
Microvelia vittigera
Cyrtorhinus lividipennis
Tetragnatha sp. 1
Callitrichia formosana
Dystiscus sp. 1
Nephotettix nigropictus
Lycosa pseudoannulata

Jul-Oct 1988 (wet season)

Nephotettix virescens
Microvelia atrolineata
Sogatella furcifera
Cyrtorhinus lividipennis
Lycosa pseudoannulata
Nephotettix nigropictus
Gryllid sp. 1
Callitrichia formosana
Gonatocerus sp. 1
Microvelia vittigera □

A method for collecting leafroller (LF) eggs on nonplant substrates

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Methods for collecting LF eggs to use in experiments and varietal screening involve caging field-collected or laboratory-reared moths on potted 30- to 40-d-old rice plants. Plants with eggs are removed daily and incubated until the larvae hatch.

The process is cumbersome, requires large cages and insectary space, and inefficient. Most eggs are laid on the walls of the cages.

We developed a new oviposition cage in which the moths lay their eggs on black cloth. Wire gauze is rolled into a 5-cm-diameter cylinder 10 cm